

THE ORIGIN, EVALUATION, AND APPLICATION OF LITERARY COMPARATIVISTICS IN LITERARY STUDIES

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Abstract

This article discussed the issues related to the origin, evaluation, and application of ad abi comparativistics in literary studies.

Keywords:

Literary studies, comparison, typology, literary comparativistics, ANVeselovsky, Franz Bopp, Rasmus Rusk, Jacob Grimm, VMJirmunsky, D.Dyurishin, NI Konrad;

While studying, analyzing and researching the masterpieces of Uzbek and world literature, we can fully understand the essence of the artistic creation, enjoy the richness and freshness of the work, smell and feel its original beauty. , we use specific analysis methods in literary studies to deeply analyze the plot, composition, form and content of the work, images, behavior of characters, spiritual and spiritual world, emotional experiences. This is it research in our work comparative-historical, comparative typological analysis methods appeal in doing comparative of literary studies content-essence, literary of comparative studies object, subject, purpose about stopping let's go to the goal according to will be

Comparative literary studies from the Latin word "comparativus" - "comparative". received is different different process and literary events comparative to learn based science is counted.

"This is it the term the first times In France ("littérature comparée", 1817), then In England ("Comparative literature" 1886), in Germany (magazine in the title «Zeitschrift für vergleichende Literaturgeschichte» - «Comparative literature history» magazine 1887-1910), in Russia (1889 ANVeselovsky) is used in research started".¹

"Comparative literary studies about initial theoretical views literary of processes similar and different sides explain the need due to the XIX century in their heads In Europe, 19th century second in half in Russia formed".²

Comparative studies direction initial studies first linguistics in the direction of his own important aspects showed later while literary studies in the field wide scope to research basis it has been. "Comparative-typological method in development Like Franz Bopp, Rasmus Rask, Jacob Grimm Europe of linguists separately contribution they are innovator linguists as to the field came out".³

Literary of comparative studies object literary is a process. Artistic literature learning with depends all issues (e.g., work plot and composition, content and form, art work

¹ G.Halliyeva. Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik. T.: "Mumumtoz so'z" nash, 2020, 7-b

² Batafsil qarang: Академические школы в литературоведении. - М., 1975.

³ Rasulov R. Umumiy tilshunoslik. - Toshkent, 2010. - B.81.

language, writer style and etc.)⁴ According to VMJirmunsky (1891–1971), the writer creativity to him effect conducted national, international literary traditions with comparatively learning too big Methodical important have being a writer creative individuality, national and the world literature in development held place to determine help will give⁵

Comparative from the analysis the goal is the comparative of objects similar and different aspects identify, they between common laws surface from release consists of⁶

21st century come national and the world peoples literature samples comparative, in particular, typological similarities in the system learning of literary studies leader principle turning around managed to In this place question is born Typological similarity, typology what?

" Typology - wool. typos — sign, trace; example, form, + logos — science, doctrine. Objects system parts separate and them using a generalized model or type from grouping consists of scientific method."⁷

"Typology - objects using abstract, generalized models (types). scientific classification to do method. In this being studied of objects the most important structure and functional features note will be done. Typology main feature is that he is not only learned, learned received objects classification do, maybe it or this period to science yet known didn't happen of objects there is be to get from before It is also possible to display (identify). gives (for example, D. I. Mendeleev elements periodic system). Scientific from universal ways of thinking one was typology being studied objects between similarity and the difference open to give them exactly analogy, equalization ways to find is based on and in many fields of science is used, however different characteristic objects a lot bio, chemistry, geog. linguistics, literary studies, psychology such as in the sciences efficient will be used."⁸

Ingliz tilidagi ochiq lug'atlarda tipologiya atamasiga quyidagicha izoh berilgan: "Typology - is the study of various traits and types, or the systematic classification of the types of something according to their common characteristics. Typology is the act of finding, counting and classifying facts with the help of eyes, other senses and logic."⁹

The world literary studies, in particular, Uzbek in literary studies typology different different literary events commonality identify giver scientific and theoretical approach, eng important methodological tool as series to research reason is happening ¹⁰Typology literary

⁴ G.Halliyeva. Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik. T.: "Mumumtoz so'z" nash, 2020, 8-b

⁵ Jirmunskiy V.M. Проблемы сравнительно-исторического изучения литератур // Известия АН. Т. XIX. Вып 3. – М., 1960. – С.183.

⁶ G.Halliyeva. Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik. T.: "Mumumtoz so'z" nash, 2020, 17-b

⁷ <https://uz.wiktionary.org/wiki/typology>

⁸ https://www.ziyouz.com/books/uzbekiston_milliy_ensiklopediyasi/Uzbekiston%20Milliy%20Ensiklopediyasi%20-%20T%20harfi.pdf

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Typology>

¹⁰ Сирожиддинов Ш. Алишер Навоий манбалари-нинг қиёсий-типологик текстологик таҳлили. – Тошкент: Академнашр, 2011; Қосимов А. Типологик ўхшашликлар ва ўзаро таъсирнинг назарий муаммолари (А.де Сент-Экзюпери ва А.Камю ижоди мисолида). Филол. фан. докт... дисс. – Тошкент, 2007; Бабаева С.Р. Сравнительно-типологические исследования произведений М.Твена и Г.Гуляма. Филология и искусствоведение. Вестник ЧПУ, 2011; Жўракулов У. Алишер Навоий «Хамса»сида хронотоп поэтикаси. Филол. фан. докт... дисс. – Тошкент, 2017.; Халлиева Г.И. XX аср рус шарқшунослигида ўзбек мумтоз адабиёти тадқиқи. Филол. фан. докт...дисс. – Тошкент, 2016.; Мирзаева З.И. XX аср ўзбек адабиётининг Америкада ўрганилиши. Филол. фан. докт... дисс. – Тошкент, 2017.; Жўраев Ж.О. Шарафиддин Али Яздийнинг «Рисолаи муаммо»си текстологик ва қиёсий-типологик тадқиқи. Филол. фан. докт... дисс. – Тошкент, 2019.;

effect as a result each other requirement two and from him more than literary processes comparative to study directed literary studies method being is considered Comparativist studies in particular Literary scholar scientist Suvan Meli : " Literature and art samples more sure and deep study demand as a result comparativism , comparative-historical method such as literary check methods to the body came Typology this method and of methods relatively more private one way is ... Binary typology typological for comparison based on of research the most wide spread out type is considered Because only double , two divided only thing to compare possible , one thing while for comparison does not descend ... That is comparison to be for at least two event to be necessary Binary of typology each on the ground now -he supervision from that . One next to second event appear to be with , that's it immediately comparison to the body will come . Even them comparison is also necessary not standing next to each other own mind potential comparison gives birth Potential comparison while whole of the universe gross property to say worthy " ¹¹ . " Literature revolutions in the dictionary typology about : " Typological relations - literary events (works , writers style , literary currents , directions , whole head literary periods) between certain consanguinity or similar conditions with marked , even of writers himself not understood by either ideological reality , objective relations , " compatibility " (Jirmunsky). is called¹²

D. Dyurishin literature typological learning direction in the world the most big expert , famous slovak is a scientist . He is himself in their research typological the analysis of literary studies important issues one as confession is enough and his task literary of influence essence identify , internal laws from opening consists of emphasizes¹³ D. Dyurishin typological similarities three type separate to learn recommendation does :

1. Socio-typological similarities . In this social of conditions of the work ideological-philosophical in the content reflection reach mean is caught . Social and ideological factors artistic work to the composition embedded is , especially , ideological content of the author era , social to the system relatively philosophical their views in expression obvious manifestation will be In this in literature own on the contrary found science , art fields and legal mind development impulse giver socio-political , ideological views , morals about problems with depends events scope mean is caught .

2. Literary-typological similarities . This is it kind of similarities pure literary to the event is based on of literature this field comparative-typological of research object exactly that's it there is literature theory with will unite . Artistic in the work common and different aspects not only literary direction , genres point of view from the point of view , maybe ideological and psychological approach , heroes description , composition , plot , motives , images system , descriptive tools , poetry structure elements like artistry provider components point of view in terms of learning literary studies for important results will give . Literary scholar scientist Sh.Sirojiddinov Alisher Navoi of sources comparative-typological

Исмоилов И.А. Алишер Навоий «Садди Искандарий» достонининг қиёсий таҳлили. Филол.фан. бўйича фалс.докт.(PhD) дисс... – Тошкент, 2019.; Кабирова Н. Раҳнавард Зарёб хикояларининг поэтикаси (образлар талқини, бадий тасвир ва услуб масалалари) Филол.фан. бўйича фалс. докт. (PhD) дисс...– Тошкент, 2020.; Суванов З. Тоғай Мурод насрида образлар поэ-тикаси. Филол.фан. бўйича фалс.докт.(PhD) дисс... – Тошкент, 2019.

¹²Словарь литературоведческих терминов. – М.: Просвещение, 1974. – С. 114.

¹³ Batafsil qarang: Dyurishin D. Теория сравнительного изучения литературы.– М., 1979.

textological to the analysis dedicated monograph literary-typological similarities analysis done scientific from the works is ¹⁴considered

3. Psychological-typological similarities . Modern in literary studies artistic of the work literary in process place designation in order to creative of the person known one the work individual psychological in creation inclination attention is taken .¹⁵

In life to each other similar events many occurs , repeats and naturally , artistic literature them his own image to the object turns Literary critic NI Konrad's " Comparative-typological of research task from each other independent respectively appear was of events typological commonality discover reach " It is possible , " he ¹⁶said thoughts our our comments correctness confirms .

Artistic of images comparative-typological study within each one work idea generality , content commonality to be it is necessary Images character , spiritual world , spiritual his world , his " I". with separateness occupation reach need

¹⁴ Sirojiddinov Sh. Alisher Navoiy manbalarining qiyosiy-tipologik teksto-logik tahlili. – Toshkent: Akademiya nashri, 2011.

¹⁴ G.Halliyeva. Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik. T.: "Mumumtoz so'z" nash, 2020, 59-b

¹⁴Н. И. Конрад. Запад и Восток. – М.: Политиздат, 1972. Ст. 295.